

ПЕДАГОГИК ВА ПСИХОЛОГИК ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES

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THE MAIN ASPECTS OF FORMING COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

ANNOTATION

The formation of communication skills in children of junior school age, practical methods of researching the child's personality, and the main aspects of the formation of social behavior patterns in the child's personality are discussed.

Key words: Communication, skill, social aspects, child's personality, social, behavior.

BOSHLANG‘ICH MAKTAB O‘QUVCHILARIDA MULOQOT KO‘NIKMALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING ASOSIY JIHLTLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda muloqot ko‘nikmalarining shakllantirishi, bola shaxsini tadqiq etishga doir amaliy metodikalar hamda bola shaxsida ijtimoiy xulq-atvor namunalarining shakllanishining asosiy jihatlari to‘g‘risida so‘z yuritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Muloqot, ko‘nikma, ijtimoiy jihatlar, bola shaxsi, ijtimoiy, xulq-atvor.

ОСНОВНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ НАВЫКОВ У УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Рассмотрены формирование коммуникативных навыков у детей младшего школьного возраста, практические методы исследования личности ребенка, а также основные аспекты формирования моделей социального поведения личности ребенка.

Ключевые слова: Коммуникация, умения, социальные аспекты, личность ребенка, социальное поведение.

Introduction.

Today, in our republic, the fundamental improvement of the regulatory framework in the field of general education, the integration of advanced foreign experiences, scientific developments and technologies into the activities of general education institutions, and the support of scientific and innovative pedagogical activities in the field of early development of children of junior school age. conceptual reforms aimed at in the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Fundamentally improving the quality of general secondary education, in-depth study of important and high-demand subjects such as foreign languages and informatics, mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology" 1 was targeted [1].

The formation of communication skills in children of primary school age, practical methods of researching the child's personality and the formation of social behavior patterns in the child's personality M.G. Davletshin, E.G'.G'oziyev, B.R. Kadirov, V.M. Karimova, A.M. Jabborov, Z.T. Nishonova, Z.P. Qilicheva, A.Kadirova, M.A. Norbosheva was researched by O'.B.Shamsiev, M.A. Narbasheva, and Sh.J.Bekovalar. V.V. Davidov, A.V. Petrovsky, communication tools, material and spiritual qualities created as a result of communication in their scientific views were researched by A. A. Leontev, B.F. Lomov, B.D. Parigin, AGRuzskaya, Ye.O.Smirnova, A.P. Usova, V.V. Davidov, I.L. Zimnyaya, L.S. Usova, R. S Burelar. The importance of developing children's speech, speech as a method of communication, development of its communicative function has been studied in many works of different authors (AABadalev, AABuyeva, S. Vygotsky, AALEontev, MILisina, etc.).

Review of literature: Modern pedagogical practice is based on psychological and pedagogical research that theoretically substantiates the essence and importance of the formation of communicative skills in the development of a child. Many studies are based on the concept of activity developed by V.V.Davidov, A.V.Zaporogest, A.N.Leontev, D.B.Elkonin and others. Based on it, MILisina, AGRuzskaya considered communication as a communicative activity. Conducted research shows that communication skills help the child's mental development (A.V.Zaporogest, M.I. Lisina, A.G. Ruzskaya), which is reflected in the scientific works of psychologists.

Foreign scientists Z.Freid, A.Freid, A.Bandura, A.Thomas have developed models of international communication competence formation in students. Problems of formation of students' independent communication skills in the educational process have been researched in scientific works. It is one of the important tasks of the present day to make the students of junior school age mature in all respects, with good morals and good manners.

Because this thing arises from the issue of increasing the effectiveness of education and upbringing in the process of restoring national values and morale. In the study of this problem, it is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics of students, in order to properly implement primary education on a scientific basis, in order to successfully implement the task facing psychologists.

The main part educational activity provides an opportunity for a student of junior school age not only for the high level of cognitive development, but also for the development of personal characteristics. In addition to leading learning activities, other activities such as play, communication and work have a direct impact on the development of the student's personality.

On the basis of these activities, the personal characteristics associated with motivation to achieve success begin to form. Also creates an opportunity to It is to achieve this position or position that the child can try to study well. Children of this age constantly compare their own success with that of their peers.

It is extremely important for them to always be the first. In children of this age, the motive to enter the competition is considered a constant need, and this motive gives them a strong emotional tension. These characteristics actually begin in kindergarten and become more apparent in elementary school and adolescence. Children's self-esteem depends on the teacher's assessment and their success in various activities.

Characteristics of children of this age such as trustworthiness, openness, susceptibility to external influences, and obedience create a good opportunity to educate them as individuals. This period is the period of emergence and strengthening of the child's main personality traits, which determine the child's success in various activities.

During this period, motivations for success are formed, and qualities such as hard work and independence are strengthened. For the formation of independence, it is extremely important to give the child more independent tasks and to give confidence.

Similarly, it is necessary to create such a socio-psychological environment in which the child should be entrusted with the task of performing an independent, social task, and in the process of performing this task, the child should feel that he is the leader of his peers, adults and other people. It is this feeling that creates motivations for the child to be independent. A school-aged child understands his individual characteristics.

The child's self-awareness also develops rapidly and becomes stronger. During this period, children begin to attach more importance to their names and try to be positively accepted by their peers and those around them. A child's assessment of his appearance and body structure is also of great importance in his self-awareness. By the end of elementary school, children, especially girls, begin to pay special attention to their facial features. In the course of their educational activities, they develop the ability to coordinate their own behavior and activities, develop the ability to consciously come to an opinion, develop interest in self-organization of their activities and the process of learning. helps to make a decision.

What motivates student behavior also changes. In this case, the opinions of friends and the team will be the main motives. Moral feelings and volitional characteristics of a person are formed. The child's characteristics, which are visible at the age of 5-6, develop and strengthen over the years. That's why proverbs such as "From the beginning of childhood" are often found in the works of the folk ogzaki [6].

By the beginning of adolescence, many personal qualities can be formed. Children's individuality is also evident in their cognitive processes. During this period, children's knowledge expands and deepens, their skills and abilities improve. By grades 3-4, the general and special abilities of some students are noticeable. In junior school age, the motivation to achieve success, which is extremely important for life, is strengthened, which automatically leads to the rapid development of other abilities.

It is known that in order to set up the activity of forming the student's personality in an exemplary way, it is necessary to find the appropriate content of their character traits and personal characteristics. It makes it possible to have an individual relationship with the subject taken separately after identifying each student individually.

The personal qualities of an 8-10-year-old child are unstable, their outlook is simple, and they are easily influenced by external impressions. As noted by the great scholars, a person's character is formed most of all in the early knowledge of his life, and the quality manifested in this character is firmly established and becomes the strong nature of the child. Primary school teacher is responsible for instilling positive emotions, personal qualities in the child's second nature, and forming high human qualities in them. If we dwell on the researches of this period, we should especially emphasize the researches and ideas of E. Erikson, Z. Freud, G.A.Sukerman and V.V. Rubsov, K.S. Vygotsky and D.B. Elkonin.

They emphasized that children's mental and personal development can be achieved through their relationship with the people around them, the class team, the teacher, and their parents. The communication between students and the teacher of junior school age begins with the period of adaptation to the educational process. Pupils have a desire to communicate with the teacher not only privately, but also confidentially. Communication of elementary school age students with the teacher also affects the motives of educational activities and relationships with peers.

By the 3rd-4th grade, the relationship with his peers becomes more important for the child. Adults can use these relationships for educational purposes. Children of this age can spend hours alone doing their hobbies, and on this basis, they develop the qualities of hard work and independence. The terms hard work and enjoyment of work represent the main themes of this period, during which children are busy trying to find out what is made of what and how it works.

The child's "Ego" conformity is now expressed as follows: "I" - what I have learned to do. Children study at school and join the rules of order and discipline in which active participation is understood. A person who is concerned with school procedures is a perfect performer. The peculiarity of this period is that the feeling of dissatisfaction with oneself, doubting one's abilities or one's position among peers is a manifestation of inexperience [5].

At this young age of the student, every word said by the teacher, a behavior, a method of influence becomes a criterion of truth for him. Because students trust their teachers very strongly, listen to their opinions and opinions, are very impressed by pedagogical tact, and strictly follow their requirements. From this point of view, they try to solve all the tasks given by the pedagogue, problem situations created, and try to fulfill them on time. High trust in the teacher, direct imitation of him, the perception of a person by a person is similar to the stage of identification.

From this period:

- 1) external influence on the student's psyche;
- 2) encouraging people to help people in the environment;
- 3) giving instructions and guidance on what to do;
- 4) to explain to him the sense of duty of a simple individual or social nature;
- 5) to teach him to think correctly;
- 6) to support his positive feelings and good intentions;
- 7) to discuss together the book you read, the movie you watched, the incident that happened in the classroom, the impressions of the trip;
- 8) the possibility to teach students to refrain from inappropriate words and expressions, to prevent conflict;
- 9) to enjoy nature scenes and listen to music appears. All these factors play an important role in the formation of a student as a person [4].

Children's emotions change depending on the conditions of how educational activities are organized. In this way, emotional control and emotional stability are observed in students of junior school age. By this time, they can control their emotions and moods. Because their emotions are calmer, deeper and more balanced than those of preschoolers and teenagers.

They have long-term positive emotions, cheerfulness, and a cheerful mood. When children come to school for the first time, a new system of relationships and a circle of communication is formed. From the first days of school, students do not pay attention to each other, are not interested in the achievements of their peers, and rarely engage in communication. But over time, students gradually begin to observe each other, feel the need for communication and begin to make friends with their peers. by the end of primary education, the need to occupy a special place among students begins to form.

Interest in the educational achievements of peers begins to increase, and the desire to stand out from them becomes the main motive of behavior. The formation of their personality also depends on cooperation in educational activities. Since communication is a very complex process, it is very difficult to give it a single correct definition.

Therefore, the content of the concept of communication is usually defined by emphasizing some of its aspects.

A) communication - the process of establishing communication and developing it based on the need for cooperation.

B) communication - interaction of subjects through the sign system.

In the textbook "General Psychology" published under the editorship of A. V. Petrovsky, communication is recognized as a process consisting of information exchange, interaction and mutual understanding between two or more people. In the textbook "General Psychology" published by M.G. Davletshin, communication is an interaction between two or more people consisting of the exchange of information of an affective evaluative nature and knowledge.

In the short explanatory dictionary "Psychology" published under the guidance of M.G.Davletshin, communication is defined as the interaction of two or more people can be defined as follows: communication is a process of interaction between at least two people, during which information is exchanged, relations are established and developed.

It is known that the periods of growth, development and formation of any person cannot be realized without educational activities. Mental development and education are closely related activities. If the student does not show activity in the educational process, the activities carried out will not give the intended result. It is also important to teach students to work independently in the educational process.

The main activity of children of primary school age is reading. Educational activities create new conditions for the child's speech, thinking, ability development. After coming to school, the child changes to a new system of relations with others from a psychological point of view. He begins to feel the need to radically change his life, to submit to new obligations, to the requirements of educational activities, to go to school every day. The fact that the family members are interested in the achievements of the child's educational activities, as well as the fact that they control him, the new form of attitude towards him is the basis for the change of attitude towards him, to fully feel that his social status has changed.

Through all the opportunities in the educational process, the scope of their knowledge acquisition expands, their interests increase, the ability to creatively search develops, the activity of thinking, independence increases, and the use of mental potential is created. They are devoted to everything and have the opportunity to carefully distinguish between them, generalize, draw conclusions. As soon as the child enters school, the attitude towards him and the creation of opportunities and conditions for his unique mental development through students imposes a great sense of responsibility on the family and school education system.

Conclusion, it can be said that when communicating with a child and determining the levels of behavior, meeting their needs such as the environment, age characteristics, receiving and transmitting information, interacting with peers and adults, and following the norms of group work shows the importance of gradually learning the formation of communication skills. In mastering the lesson processes in the primary class, the development of mental-intellectual movements, the development of verbal thinking, the formation of emotional communication, the skills and interests of children are used by adults. Attention and other aspects can create the basis for the formation of more communication skills.

One of the important goals of the education policy implemented in our country is to educate the young generation to become well-rounded people. Of course, a perfect person means a person who is spiritually mature, who cares about the history, present and future of his country, and who is passionate about contributing to the economic development of society. But if we take an analytical approach to this concept, it is possible to understand how rich, complex and comprehensively it corresponds to universal human values. In this case, we rely on the scientific knowledge that is considered necessary for the psychological, spiritual and intellectual development of children in the junior school age.

When a child steps on the threshold of school, the need to be interested in his friends and the need to receive a sense of gratitude begins to form, that is, this situation is characterized by the motives of getting attention from partners or achieving a high level of brilliance. The scientists of our country, in contrast to the above-mentioned foreign researchers, paid a lot of attention to the ethnopsychological aspects of the problem through aspects related to the ontogenetic and family environment factors.

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